

AN INTRODUCTION TO A TAI MUONG VARIETY SPOKEN IN CHÂU PHONG COMMUNE (QUỖ CHÂU DISTRICT, NGHỆ AN PROVINCE, VIETNAM)

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Abstract

This introduction to Tai Muong, a Tai dialect of Western Nghệ An, is based on a variety of Tai Muong spoken by Lương Thị Dung, a speaker from Châu Phong Commune (Quỳ Châu District, Nghệ An Province, Vietnam). It is intended to accompany an audio word list consisting of 40 recordings: selected from the recordings made by Lương Thị Dung, those 40 recordings have already been uploaded to Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7471498>). Based on the F0 measurements obtained for each tone in the monosyllabic words she recorded, a tone diagram was created.

Keywords: Tai Muong, Tai dialects of Western Nghệ An (Vietnam), tone systems

ISO 639-3 codes: tyj

The speaker, Lương Thị Dung, 28 years old at the time of the first interviews, is from Châu Phong Commune, Quỳ Châu District, Nghệ An Province. She calls the Tai dialect she speaks “Tai Muong”, but she mentions that it is also called “Tai Yo” by some speakers in the same area. I worked online with her first from February to April 2021, and then again in February 2022. The languages she uses in her daily life are Vietnamese and Tai Muong. She can read and write English, and she says that she also understands Lao and Thai.

In the region where she lives, the language name “Tai Muong” refers to the Tai dialects spoken in this Western part of Nghệ An (e.g., Tai Yo and Tai Pao), when not Tai Daeng varieties. According to James R. Chamberlain (1984, 1991), Mène, or Tai Maen, nowadays spoken in a few districts (Khamkeuth, Viengthong, etc.) of Bolikhamxay Province (Laos), is related to these Tai dialects of Western Nghệ An.

Map 1: From google maps (<https://www.google.com/maps>) @2022 Google.

If we follow Chamberlain (1991:118-119), “Mène is a language that shows: many but not a complete set of Northern Branch lexical features; a few forms typical of the Central Branch languages; and a large amount of Southwestern Branch vocabulary.” He further suggests that “Mène is thus best characterized as a NT language with significant exposure to SWT languages.” Against that placement, Michel Ferlus (2008:309), referring specifically to a Tai Yo variety spoken in Quỳ Châu, states that, with the exception of a short list of words, the vocabulary of Western Nghệ An Tai dialects is Southwestern Tai.

Although the Tai dialects of Western Nghệ An seem to share many characteristics, it is important to take into account their diversity, as well as the ethnolinguistic background of the particular groups linked to their varieties, before speaking of them as subdialects of a same language.

The Tai Muong lexical items which the speaker recorded were first submitted to her in Vietnamese. On the basis of the F0 measurements obtained for each tone in the monosyllabic words she recorded, a tentative tone diagram (Gedney 1972) was created and subsequently included in a presentation at the 31st Annual Meeting of the Southeast Asian Linguistics Society (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rgZPU8Vxp8U>).

Figure 1: *The tone diagram for the Tai Muong variety of Châu Phong Commune, Quỳ Châu District.*

Initial\Tone	A	B	C	DL	DS
1 Voiceless friction sounds, *s, hm, ph, etc.	[¹¹³ [³²³	[³¹	[⁴³³	[²²¹	[⁴⁴⁵
2 Voiceless unaspirated stops, *p, etc.					
3 Glottal, *ʔ, ʔb, etc.	[²²⁵				
4 Voiced, *b, m, l, z, etc.	[³⁵		[⁴³¹		[²²¹

A particular feature of this tone diagram is that the DL column has only one tone [221]. This tone also appears in the DS4 box of the DS column, and one can posit a merger DL1234 = DS4, because DL syllables are of the same duration as DS4 syllables in the variety spoken by this speaker (the overall average for syllable duration in the DL column was found to be 0.15 secs). Ferlus (2008:305-306) noted the same feature in the Tai Yo variety of Quỳ Châu for which he gives a tone diagram, but his account contains a confusion between the etymology of the syllables and the tone itself. Even if DL syllables are pronounced short in that variety, they remain etymologically long syllables and cannot be considered as DS4 syllables (DS2 syllables in Ferlus’ presentation).

As against the Tai Yo variety of Quỳ Châu documented by Ferlus which displays a 123-4 split in the B column, the Tai Muong variety spoken by the speaker in the same district has no split in this column. Other cases of Western Nghệ An Tai dialects with no split in the B column include:

- a “Tay Muong” variety, also referred to as “Tay Pao”, spoken in Tương Dương District, Nghệ An Province (Ferlus 2008:309-311);
- the Mène of Khamkeuth District (Bolikhambxay Province, Laos) documented by Chamberlain (1991:108);
- and also some Tai Yo varieties investigated by Sầm Công Danh, which he recently discussed in a presentation at the 31st Annual Meeting of the Southeast Asian Linguistics Society (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rLQ0Ucr85lw>).

With respect to the 12-3-4 split in the A column, further interactions with the speaker in February 2022 confirmed this feature, which reflects a diversity of rising tones in that particular column. This split can be compared with the 123-4 split in A in most Tai Yo varieties on the one hand and with the 12-34 split in a Tai Yo variety in Quỳ Hợp District documented by Sầm Công Danh on the other.

From the words, phrases, or sentences recorded by the speaker, the following items were selected to provide examples of monosyllabic words for each of the twenty boxes in Gedney's tone diagram (Pacquement 2022).

1. ngon [cɛ:p^{DL4}] 'tasty'; 2. đi [pa:A⁴] 'go'; 3. cá [mɛ:B⁴ pa:A²] 'fish'; 3. cá [pa:A²] 'fish'; 4. gà [mɛ:B⁴ kaj^{B2}] 'chicken'; 5. vai [ba:B³] 'shoulder'; 6. mệt [nuaj^{B1}] 'tired'; 7. ăn [kin^{A2}] 'eat'; 7. muốn ăn [za:k^{DL3} ki:A⁴] 'want to eat'; 8. trời [fa:C⁴] 'sky'; 9. mưa [fon^{A1}] 'rain'; 10. trứng [saj^{B1}] 'egg'; 10. trứng [ma:k^{DL1} saj^{B1}] 'egg'; 11. kiến [mɛ:B⁴ mot^{DS4}] 'ant'; 12. ếch [mɛ:B⁴ k^hiat^{DL1}] 'small frog'; 13. chim [mɛ:B⁴ nok^{DS4}] 'bird'; 14. muốn [za:k^{DL3}] 'want'; 14. muốn có [za:k^{DL3} daj^{C3}] 'want to have'; 14. muốn làm [za:k^{DL3} ʔi:B³ ʔe:A⁴] 'want to do'; 15. ba [p^hɔ:B⁴, pɔ:B⁴, ʔa:j^{C3}] 'father'; 16. mẹ, má [mɛ:C⁴, ʔu:j^{A3}, ʔɛ:j^{C3}] 'mother'; 17. mặt trăng [ma:k^{DL1} buan^{A3}] 'moon'; 18. sao [ma:k^{DL1} da:w^{A3}] 'star'; 19. nấm [het^{DS1}] 'mushroom'; 20. rau [p^hak^{DS1}] 'vegetable'; 21. thích [ʔi:B³] 'like, love'; 22. móng tay móng chân [lep^{DS4} ti:n^{A2} lep^{DS4} mu:A⁴] 'nails of the hands, nails of the feet'; 23. bụng [pu:m^{A2}] 'stomach'; 24. răng [hɛ:w^{C1}] 'tooth'; 25. máu [luat^{DL4}] 'blood'; 26. xương [kaʔ du:k^{DL3}] 'bone'; 27. em gái [nɔ:ɲ^{C4} sa:w^{A1}] 'younger sister', chị [ʔɛ:j^{C3} sa:w^{A1}] 'elder sister'; 28. em trai [nɔ:ɲ^{C4} ca:j^{A4}] 'younger brother'; 29. con vắt [mɛ:B⁴ ta:k^{DL4}] 'land leech'; 30. sấm [fa:C⁴ luam^{C1} p^hɛ:C¹] 'thunder'; 31. dao [veɲ^{A4}] 'knife'; 32. vào [haw^{C1}] 'enter'; 33. rừng [pa:B²] 'forest'; 34. đen [dam^{A3}] 'black', đỏ [dap^{A3}] 'red', đẹp [di:A³] 'beautiful', bay [bin^{A3}] 'fly'.

1-10: một [nuw^{B1}]; hai [sɔ:ɲ^{A1}]; ba [sa:m^{A1}]; bốn [si:B¹]; năm [ha:C¹]; sáu [hok^{DS1}]; bảy [cɛt^{DS2}]; tám [pɛ:t^{DL2}]; chín [kaw^{C2}]; mười [sip^{DS1}].

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